

Numerical parametric study of finned surfaces for enhanced cooling

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Abstract

An alternative cooling approach for a new fuel cell-powered aircraft engine looks towards the usage of the nacelle surface as an external heat exchanger, on which fins are attached for heat transfer enhancement. To gain insight on the fin design, a numerical parametric study is carried out via RANS simulations to quantify the heat transfer against the drag that a finned flat plate configuration would present. Results show that scaling the fins vertically would enhance heat transfer, although with high drag gain, as well as becoming inefficient due to limited solid thermal conductivity, giving insight for future design considerations.

1. Introduction

The FAMEⁱ project focuses on the design of a new fuel cell powered aircraft engine, on which the exploration of the concept of external cooling via the nacelle surface is contemplated. Kellerman et al¹ showcases the potential for such a concept, although noting that the heat transfer capability is strongly limited to the available wetted surface, being the nacelle surface relatively small compared to the fuselage or wings. In order to increase the wetted surface of a nacelle, attaching fins to it is considered, which would indeed increase the amount of heat transferred to the air flow, although increasing the total drag of the body as well.

Fin theory exists in literature such as of Cengel & Ghajar² and applied on a vast number of applications where the convective heat transfer coefficient is weak, such as in slow speed flows. This establishes the design of large and multiple fins, which strongly enhance heat transfer with a small drag increase due to the low dynamic pressure of such applications. Nevertheless, for our current application, convective heat transfer is already strong due to the large speed of the flow, implying that a careful design of the fins should be considered to avoid large gains of drag for low gains of convective heat transfer. Therefore, for the current study, a specific fin configuration was established, being presented in figure 1, on which a numerical parametric analysis is performed to gain insight on the physics at play.

Figure 1: Fin configuration (left) and front view of single fin (right).

The numerical simulations are performed using the software ANSYS FLUENT 21R2 and involve a turbulent boundary layer (BL) flow over a flat plate, which eventually passes through the heated fin configuration. These results are compared to a clean flat plate with no fins to analyze the gained heat transfer and drag. The cases of the simulation imply scaling the fin configuration horizontally or vertically, effectively changing its dimensions and, therefore, the

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way it interacts with the BL. For the analysis, two thermo-hydraulic performance parameters are established, which are used as a ratio between the amount of heat transferred vs. the drag gained by adding fins to the flat plates, which are parameters similar to those defined in the studies of Webb & Eckert,³ Liao et al⁴ and Mhetras et al.⁵ The fin efficiency is studied as well by considering the thermal conductivity through the solid fin, becoming conjugate heat transfer (CHT) simulations in which the solid thermal conductivity is varied. The reference conditions for the simulations follow the ones that the FAME aircraft engine presents during cruise at an altitude of 8230 m (27 000 ft), being these conditions displayed in table 1.

Table 1: Reference parameters at cruise conditions

Property	Symbol	Units	Magnitude
Reference length	L_{ref}	m	5
Reference area	A_{ref}	m ²	0.05
Freestream speed	U_∞	m/s	168.9
Static pressure	P_∞	Pa	34 761
Freestream density	ρ_∞	kg/m ³	0.516
Freestream temperature	T_∞	K (°C)	234.7 (-38.5)
Total temperature	T_0	K (°C)	248.9 (-24.8)
Surface temperature	T_w	K (°C)	375.5 (102.3)
Reynolds number	Re_L	-	$2.82 \cdot 10^7$
Mach number	Ma_∞	-	0.55
Prandtl number	Pr_∞	-	0.75
Temperature ratio	R_T	-	1.6

2. Thermo-hydraulic performance parameters

Taking a reference area of A_{ref} , the drag coefficient c_d and the average Stanton number \overline{St} of a surface or fin configuration can be obtained through equations (1) and (2), respectively, where $\Delta T = T_w - T_r$.

$$c_d = \frac{D}{0.5 \rho_\infty U_\infty^2 A_{ref}} \quad (1)$$

$$\overline{St} = \frac{Q_T}{\rho_\infty C_p U_\infty \Delta T A_{ref}} \quad (2)$$

The recovery temperature T_r is defined in equation (3) as the temperature towards which heat is transferred, being this higher than T_∞ since its definition allows to take into account effects of heating due to viscous work on a turbulent BL, as stated by Schlichting & Gersten.⁶

$$T_r = T_\infty + Pr_\infty \frac{U_\infty^2}{2 C_p} \quad (3)$$

From here, the thermo-hydraulic performance parameters β and γ are defined in equations (4) and (5), respectively. While β evaluates the performance based on the ratio between the total heat transferred and the total drag force D , γ does the same but based only on the viscous component of the drag force D_v . This distinction is made since γ analyzes the correlation that the heat flux presents with the available wall shear stress, being this related to the physics of heat transfer. On the other hand, β includes the effect of pressure and separation, an effect that can be reduced by reshaping the fin into a more aerodynamic geometry. As the pressure drag diminishes due to improved design, $\beta \rightarrow \gamma$ for a fin.

$$\beta = \frac{2 Pr_\infty}{R_T^{0.059}} \left(\frac{\overline{St}}{c_d} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{2 Pr_\infty}{R_T^{0.059}} \left(\frac{\overline{St}}{c_d} \right) \left(\frac{D}{D_v} \right) \quad (5)$$

In the case of a flat plate entirely heated to a constant T_w , equation (6) is satisfied, starting from the integration of the skin friction c_f vs. Re_x and Stanton number St vs. Re_x distributions over the entire flat plate length, being these distributions presented in equations (7) and (8), respectively, which are valid for high values of Re_x as presented

by Kays & Crawford.⁷ The term between brackets corresponds to compressibility effects due to Ma_∞ described by Schlichting & Gersten,⁶ while R_T corresponds to wall heating effects as shown by Gersten & Herwig.⁸ It is noted that the coefficients of the present equations were calibrated based on numerical simulations performed on an entirely heated flat plate using the SST $k-\omega$ model of Menter⁹ for different values of Re_L , $0.1 < Ma_\infty < 0.7$ and $1.2 < R_T < 2.0$, obtaining a set of almost 40 data points. As an example, results of the obtained c_d and \overline{St} for 8 data sets are presented in table 2.

$$\overline{St}_{fp} = \frac{1}{2} c_{d,fp} Pr_t^{-1} R_T^{0.059} \quad (6)$$

$$c_f = 0.02528 Re_x^{-1/7} \left[1 + Pr_t \frac{k-1}{4} Ma_\infty^2 \right]^{-1} R_T^{-0.372} \quad (7)$$

$$St = \frac{1}{2} 0.02528 Re_x^{-1/7} Pr_t^{-1} \left[1 + Pr_t \frac{k-1}{4} Ma_\infty^2 \right]^{-1} R_T^{-0.313} \quad (8)$$

Table 2: Results of numerical simulation of a flat plate for different Re_L , Ma_∞ and R_T

Re_L [10 ⁶]	Ma_∞ 1	R_T 1	c_d [10 ⁻³]	\overline{St} [10 ⁻³]	Re_L [10 ⁶]	Ma_∞ 1	R_T 1	c_d [10 ⁻³]	\overline{St} [10 ⁻³]
2.1	0.1	1.2	3.5	2.1	6.2	0.1	1.2	2.9	1.8
2.1	0.1	2.0	2.9	1.8	6.2	0.1	2.0	2.4	1.5
14.9	0.7	1.2	2.5	1.5	43.3	0.7	1.2	2.2	1.3
14.9	0.7	2.0	2.1	1.3	43.3	0.7	2.0	1.8	1.1

By substitution of equation (6) on equations (4) and (5), a value of $\beta_{FP} = \gamma_{FP} = 1$ is obtained for a flat plate since $D = D_v$ applies due to the lack of pressure drag D_p on it. Therefore, the value of $\beta = 1$ and $\gamma = 1$ is used as a reference when analyzing the finned configurations since, at the end, they closely resemble flat plates attached to the surface. Configurations with $\gamma < 1$ would not be desired, while configurations of $\gamma > 1$ would be of high interest. It is of additional interest as well to explore fin configurations with $\beta \rightarrow \gamma$, where D_p is minimized since this force component does not have any direct correlation with the heat transfer of the fin, as D_v has with Q_T following flat plate theory.

3. Flat plate & fins

The study involves comparing the resultant integral parameters of a flat plate with heated fins with those of a clean flat plate with a heated zone, being this zone the same as where the fins would be attached. A schematic of the clean flat plate, as well as of the finned flat plate is presented in figure 2. It can be seen that geometries are divided by regions, from which their corresponding values of Q , D_v and D are used to compute their values of drag coefficient c_d and average Stanton number \overline{St} as defined in equations (1) and (2), respectively, as well as to compute their values of β and γ following their formulations presented in equations (4) and (5), respectively.

The flat plate presents an unheated entry region of length $L_1 = 0.5$ m, a heated region of length $L_2 = L_{fin} = 1$ m and an unheated exit region of length $L_3 = 3.5$ m, making a total $L_{ref} = L_1 + L_2 + L_3 = 5$ m, as noted on table 1. Following figure 1, the dimensions of the reference fin configuration are presented in table 3. The selection of such a configuration is based on its simplicity, its height H_{fin} is on the order of the BL thickness for the selected L_{ref} and Re_L , and Z_{fin} were chosen since an R_A around 5 or 6 was required.

For the finned flat plate, the heating is done under the fins base, allowing heat to pass through it and into the fluid, implying physics of CHT which are taken into account in the numerical simulation, as long as the thermal conductivity of the solid λ_{sol} is finite. Therefore, the fins are set-up as solid made of aluminum ($\lambda_{sol} = \lambda_{alu} = 202.4 \text{ W}/(\text{m} \cdot \text{K})$), although simulations which disregard CHT are carried with no solid heat resistance ($\lambda_{sol} \rightarrow \infty$) to evaluate the efficiency of the fin configuration η_{sim} , defined in equation (9), being $Q_{T,CHT}$ obtained from simulations considering CHT, while $Q_{T,ideal}$ do not consider it.

$$\eta_{sim} = \frac{Q_{T,CHT}}{Q_{T,ideal}} \quad (9)$$

Still, fin theory shown by Cengel & Ghajar² supplies correlation to calculate a theoretical fin configuration efficiency η_{theo} for rectangular fin arrangements with infinite length, which, if accommodated to the present study,

Figure 2: Clean flat plate (left) and finned flap plate (right) geometries for numerical simulations. Grey zones correspond to heated zones.

Table 3: Reference geometrical parameters of the studied fin configuration

Property	Symbol	Units	Magnitude
Fin streamwise length	L_{fin}	m	1
Fin spanwise length	Z_{fin}	m	0.01
Fin height	H_{fin}	m	0.025
Fin thickness	t_{fin}	m	0.002
Base area	A_{base}	m ²	0.010
Wetted area	A_{fin}	m ²	0.056
Height/Base ratio	R_H	-	2.5
Wetted/base area ratio	R_A	-	5.6

presents the form stated in equation (10). From here, η_{fin} is the efficiency of a single fin calculated as equation (11), which requires the parameter c_{fin} defined in equation (12) and the average heat transfer coefficient \overline{HTC} calculated as in equation (13).

$$\eta_{theo} = \frac{1 + 2\eta_{fin}R_H}{1 + 2R_H} \quad (10)$$

$$\eta_{fin} = \frac{\tanh(c_{fin}H_{fin})}{c_{fin}H_{fin}} \quad (11)$$

$$c_{fin} = \sqrt{\frac{2\overline{HTC}}{\lambda_{alu}t_{fin}}} \quad (12)$$

$$\overline{HTC} = \frac{Q_{T,ideal}}{A_{fin}\Delta T} \quad (13)$$

4. Numerical setup

A schematic of the fluid domain is presented in figure 3, where the fin is situated inside an embedded subdomain, which presents a fine 3D mesh to take into account complex 3D behavior. The rest of the domain presents a coarser mesh. It is noted that the symmetric and periodic behavior of the fin configuration was taken into account, implying that the domain only considers half of a fin. All walls present inflation layers, for which maximum values of $y_0^+ \approx 0.6$ were obtained. The entire mesh presents 2 million mesh elements, being 90% of them allocated on the embedded subdomain. The boundary conditions for the simulation follow the parameters established in table 1. All flat plate and fin surfaces were set with the no-slip condition. Heat transfer was established by setting the heated region, or the bottom of the fin, at a wall temperature T_w . The unheated regions are set as adiabatic walls. It is noted as well that the thermal conductivity through the fin is effectively simulated for the cases where CHT is considered for the calculation

Figure 3: Domain for numerical simulations. The fin is located inside an embedded subdomain, which presents a finer mesh resolution in contrast to the general subdomain.

of η_{sim} . As stated, such cases consider a $\lambda_{sol} = \lambda_{alu}$, while cases with no CHT consider a $\lambda_{sol} \rightarrow \infty$, eventually setting the surface of the fin at T_w .

The numerical simulations were carried out using the software ANSYS FLUENT 21R2. These were compressible steady state RANS simulations, taking into account the heating due to viscous work on the calculations. The simulations are considered to be fully turbulent and use the SST $k-\omega$ model of Menter.⁹ A constant turbulent Prandtl number of $Pr_t = 0.85$ was employed for the modeling of the turbulent thermal transport. For the modeling of the fluid properties, the specific heat capacity at constant pressure was considered as $C_p = 1006 \text{ J}/(\text{kg} \cdot \text{K})$, the dynamic viscosity μ and thermal conductivity λ were modeled via equations (14) and (15), respectively, being these power fits of data described by Cengel & Cimbala.¹⁰ The pressure-velocity is fully coupled in the solution. A second-order pressure scheme is used, as well as applying a second-order upwind scheme for all the relevant transport equations. A least-squares cell-based scheme is used for the calculation of gradients.

$$\mu = \mu_{\infty} \left(\frac{T}{T_{\infty}} \right)^{0.736} \quad (14)$$

$$\lambda = \lambda_{\infty} \left(\frac{T}{T_{\infty}} \right)^{0.859} \quad (15)$$

5. Results

The results for all simulated cases of the current study are presented in table 4, on which CHT is not considered ($\lambda_{sol} \rightarrow \infty$), therefore, being analogous to setting the fin surface at T_w . The discussion of the different cases is presented at the next subsection, while the effect of CHT is addressed at the last subsection.

Table 4: Simulation results for cases with ideal fin (no CHT, $\lambda_{sol} \rightarrow \infty$)

Case ID	c_d [10^{-3}]	$c_{d,1}$ [10^{-3}]	$c_{d,2}$ [10^{-3}]	$c_{d,3}$ [10^{-3}]	\overline{St}_2 [10^{-3}]	β_2	γ_2	β'_2	γ'_2
Unfinned	2.3	0.3	0.5	1.5	0.3	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20
V. Sc. x 0.5	2.8	0.3	1.2	1.3	0.7	1.00	1.13	1.25	1.47
V. Sc. x 1.0	3.8	0.3	2.5	1.0	1.4	0.90	1.05	1.14	1.37
V. Sc. x 2.0	6.3	0.3	5.6	0.5	2.8	0.82	0.98	1.04	1.31
H. Sc. x 0.5	4.5	0.3	3.1	1.0	1.5	0.83	0.94	0.99	1.15
H. Sc. x 1.0	3.8	0.3	2.5	1.0	1.4	0.90	1.05	1.14	1.37
H. Sc. x 2.0	3.4	0.3	1.9	1.1	1.0	0.84	1.14	1.07	1.61
V.H. Sc. x 0.5	2.9	0.3	1.3	1.3	0.8	0.96	1.06	1.16	1.32
V.H. Sc. x 1.0	3.8	0.3	2.5	1.0	1.4	0.90	1.05	1.14	1.37
V.H. Sc. x 2.0	5.0	0.2	4.0	0.8	1.8	0.74	1.02	0.95	1.46

5.1 Unfinned flat plate

The unfinned flat plate is heated on the zone on which fins would be attached, therefore, at $0.5 \text{ m} < x < 1.5 \text{ m}$, following figure 2. Table 4 presents the total drag c_d , with the different drag values of the different flat plate regions. As a reference, $\overline{St}_2 = 0.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ is reported. The values of β_2 and γ_2 are equal due to the lack of pressure drag, although they present values above unity. This is to the fact that the heating of the flat plate begins at position $x = 0.5 \text{ m}$, meaning that the thermal BL starts its development in an already grown momentum BL (delayed heating as shown by Kays & Crawford⁷). This effect can be visualized when comparing this zonal heating with a fully heated flat plate (equations (7) and (8)), as in figure 4, where St values for zonal heating become higher than for fully heating. Also, the effect of viscous drag reduction due to heating can be observed in the distributions of c_f .

Figure 4: c_f and St vs. x distributions of zonal heating (simulation) and full heating (equations (7) and (8)).

5.2 Effect of fin vertical scaling (V. Sc.)

Results for the distributions of $St = HTC/\rho_\infty U_\infty C_p$ on the surface of the reference fin geometry are shown in figure 5. Heat transfer is strongest towards the front of the fin. A BL is formed that develops over the fin, resulting in a decrease of St streamwise. Some regions of low St around the front of the fin can be observed, which could be attributed to separated flow regions that locally stagnate the flow, avoiding effective heat transfer.

Figure 5: St distributions over fin surface for reference fin geometry (2 parallel fins are displayed).

Figure 6 shows an overview of the velocity fields around the reference fin. Zooming into the front region of the fin, flow separation can be observed, which indeed justifies the existence of low St regions on the front, which could be resolved by streamlining the fin. A notable growth of the BL due to strong momentum loss is observed.

Figure 6: Fields of non-dimensional velocity u/U_∞ around reference fin.

By scaling up the fin configuration vertically as shown in figure 7, the fins are allowed to reach the outer region of the BL, eventually increasing their heat transfer potential due to higher velocities but at a cost of high drag gain, as well as due to the increase on wetted area due to vertical extension. Table 4 showcases the aforementioned behavior by noting that \overline{St}_2 increases several times but at a slower rate than the drag increase of the finned zone $c_{d,2}$. Therefore, the value of γ_2 reduces in comparison to the reference case by vertically scaling up. β_2 presents even a lower value than γ_2 due to the effects of added pressure drag on the fins, since after-fin separation is enhanced as the fin height increases. This suggests as well the necessity of improving the aerodynamic design of the fins, eventually making $\beta_2 \rightarrow \gamma_2$ by decreasing excessive pressure drag.

Figure 7: Vertical scaling.

Nevertheless, a very important observation is that due to this separation taking place after the finned region, $c_{d,3}$ becomes reduced as fin height increases. This slightly counters the drag increase imposed by the fins. To take into account this drag reduction on the evaluation of the thermo-hydraulic performance parameters, the alternative parameters β'_2 and γ'_2 are defined in equations (16) and (17), respectively. Here, the drag changes between the flat regions of the reference case and the actual case $\Delta c_{d,1}$ and $\Delta c_{d,3}$ are added to the drag of the finned region $c_{d,2}$.

$$\beta'_2 = \frac{2 Pr_t}{R_T^{0.059}} \left(\frac{\overline{St}_2}{c_{d,2} + \Delta c_{d,1} + \Delta c_{d,3}} \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\gamma'_2 = \frac{2 Pr_t}{R_T^{0.059}} \left(\frac{\overline{St}_2}{c_{d,2} \left(\frac{D_v}{D} \right) + \Delta c_{d,1} + \Delta c_{d,3}} \right) \quad (17)$$

The increase of γ'_2 above the reference value of 1.20 showcases that the drag that fins generate is counteracted by the drag reduction due to flow separation and gradual re-attachment. This after-fin drag reduction can be observed in the c_f vs. x distributions of the current vertical scaling cases in Figure 8, as well as in figure 9. It is noted that the x2

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vertical scaling displays certain unstable behavior, implying that non-stationary behavior develops as the fin increases its height.

Figure 8: Effect of vertical scaling (V. Sc.) on c_f vs. x distributions.

Figure 9: Effect of vertical scaling (V. Sc.) on the after-fin separation.

5.3 Effect of fin horizontal scaling (H. Sc.)

By scaling up the fin configuration horizontally, the wetted area is reduced since fins become more spaced apart, as shown in figure 10. This results in the opposite behavior as with vertically scaled configurations: heat transfer and drag are reduced, and the value of γ_2 increases. The highest values of γ_2 are achieved via horizontal scaling, implying that highly spaced fins are a proper solution for the lowest amount of gained drag, although they present the least amount of heat transfer enhancement.

The drag $c_{d,3}$ is not strongly affected by horizontal scaling, implying that this is a phenomenon exclusively related to fin height, although minor effects are seen on the highest horizontal scaling. This can be noted in the after-fin c_f reduction on figure 11, being similar in magnitude between cases.

Figure 10: Horizontal scaling.

Figure 11: Effect of horizontal scaling (H. Sc.) on c_f vs. x distributions.

5.4 Effect of fin homogeneous scaling (V.H. Sc.)

Homogeneous scaling can be visualized in figure 12. Table 4 shows that although being a combination of both scalings, homogeneous scaling displays a behavior closer to vertical scaling. This can also be observed on the c_f vs. x distributions of figure 13, where the after-fin c_f reduction can be noted. The case with x2 homogeneous scaling presents some instabilities as with the vertical scaling, implying a non-stationary behavior.

Figure 12: Homogeneous scaling.

Also, homogeneous scaling showcases higher growth of β_2 than just by vertical scaling. This is due to additional pressure drag being generated against the flow by the thickening of the fin, suggesting that homogeneous scaling should take into account further streamlining of the fin geometry.

5.5 Effect of fin thermal conductivity

CHT simulations taking into account a finite thermal conductivity inside the fin were performed to evaluate the reduction of heat transfer as expected by fin theory. Table 5 presents the results in terms of fin configuration efficiency, where the theoretical pre-calculated value η_{theo} is displayed along with the efficiency obtained from numerical simulations η_{sim} . Values of η_{theo} are close to the ones of η_{sim} , showcasing expected behaviors: As fins become higher through vertical or homogeneous scaling, their efficiencies tend to decrease. This is somehow counteracted by thickening the

Figure 13: Effect of homogeneous scaling (V.H. Sc.) on c_f vs. x distributions.

fin, as with homogeneous scaling to the point that homogeneous scaling now presents better β'_2 values than vertical scaling, where the opposite happens with an ideal fin.

Table 5: Simulation results for cases with fin including CHT ($\lambda_{sol} = \lambda_{alu}$)

Case ID	\overline{HTC}	t_{fin} [mm]	H_{fin} [mm]	R_H	η_{theo} [%]	η_{sim} [%]	\overline{St}_{CHT} [10^{-3}]	$\beta'_{2,CHT}$	$\gamma'_{2,CHT}$
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
V. Sc. x 0.5	95	2	12.5	1.25	98	97	0.7	1.21	1.41
V. Sc. x 1.0	106	2	25	2.5	92	89	1.2	1.00	1.19
V. Sc. x 2.0	116	2	50	5.0	72	68	1.9	0.68	0.83
H. Sc. x 0.5	65	1	25	5.0	90	83	1.3	0.80	0.92
H. Sc. x 1.0	106	2	25	2.5	92	89	1.2	1.00	1.19
H. Sc. x 2.0	129	4	25	1.25	96	94	0.9	0.99	1.48
V.H. Sc. x 0.5	59	1	12.5	2.5	98	95	0.7	1.09	1.23
V.H. Sc. x 1.0	106	2	25	2.5	92	89	1.2	1.00	1.19
V.H. Sc. x 2.0	140	4	50	2.5	82	79	1.4	0.73	1.10

On the other hand, horizontal scaling makes the fins thicker, showcasing an increase in their efficiency. Therefore, this is an attribute to be taken into account during fin design since, for example, the expected great increase of \overline{St} through vertical scaling can be easily reduced. Future work with fins with variable thickness is being carried out in order to keep a high fin efficiency for such cases.

6. Conclusions

Numerical simulations of a specific fin configuration were performed to gain insight into the design process of fins. This was done by scaling the established fin configuration vertically, horizontally and homogeneously, obtaining a variety of effects on integral parameters.

Increasing the fins' height through vertical scaling allows it to have more exposure to the freestream, enhancing heat transfer, but at a high drag gain. The opposite effect is obtained while scaling the fins horizontally.

The thermo-hydraulic parameters β_2 and γ_2 display that pressure drag is added on the fin configuration as its height and fin thickness increase, implying the necessity of improving the aerodynamic design of the fins through streamlining. This effectively would push $\beta_2 \rightarrow \gamma_2$.

Also, results display an after-fin c_f reduction due to separation at the back of the fin, which counters the drag increase that fins impose. This makes the established parameters β'_2 and γ'_2 more relevant than β_2 and γ_2 . Therefore, this is an effect that needs to be considered to further minimize drag gain.

Finally, the effect of conjugate heat transfer plays a role by reducing the amount of heat transferred due to limited solid thermal conductivity. This is analyzed through the fin efficiency, which decays as the fin height increases and as its thickness is reduced. This puts as a requirement the consideration of variable thickness on the fins' design.

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